

Application of single factor and L9 taguchi experimental design analysis based on different ratio of enzyme washing properties of denim fabric

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Abstract: This paper aims with Enzyme wash effect on Denim fabric. Denim washing is the vital part of finishing process to provide aged look and comfort by reducing the stiffness of garments. It is found that a garments construction is affected largely by washing especially GSM, on the other hand, physical properties in terms of tearing strength. The main objects of washing are to remove size materials to remove starch presents in fabric for soft feeling to wear the garments. The effect of Enzyme is decrease the fabric strength and increases the color fastness and rubbing fastness. A Denim Fabric of twill 3/1 construction was selected for this experiment. Then the Desizing process and then Enzyme wash process was done. Then some Physical and Mechanical tests were taken to compare the differences between the fabric properties before and after Enzyme wash. After Desizing and Enzyme wash we got GSM, Tensile strength and Color rating of the fabric. The Tensile Strength of the fabrics are decreased and increased the GSM by increasing enzyme ratio.

Keywords: Denim Fabric, Enzyme Ratio, Single Factor Experiment Design, L9 Orthogonal Experimental Design, Variable Effect.

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Introduction

The "Denim" name comes from the phrase of "Tissu de Nimes" used in the Rhone Valley of Southern France; and the "Blue jeans" similarly comes from the phrase of "Blue de Genes" used in the Italian Riviera.

The diversity of demand in the 1950s and 1960s set the manufacturers in motion to find the application of different washing techniques and the colors that can be applied to denim fabric[1]. At the end of the 1980s, formfitting, lycra skinny jeans made from denim fabric began to spread. The fact that the Jeans becomes popular in all segments led the

haute couture creators in new studies. Yves Saint Laurent, took the jeans to the podium in 1970. Designers such as Calvin Klein, Armani, and Valentino followed him[2].

Blue jeans are produced from the denim fabric dyed with indigo. Jeans become ready to be packed after the cutting, sewing, washing, rinsing, drying, and ironing processes[3]. Washing, which is one of the most important in these processes, gives different colors and effects to the fabric[4]. According to the desired effect to be exerted, the jeans undergo various treatments after pre-washing.

Indigo is a dyestuff produced from the leaves of the "indigoferatinctoria" plant. Indigo, the utilization of which dates back to 1600 BC, was found in India, Indonesia, China and Africa[5]. The blue indigo has gray, green and red tones. Paint manufacturers are making attempts in different colors with the indigo dye properties. However, the attempts have failed so far and fading of color could not be provided and fiber penetration could not be blocked. Since indigo does not penetrate into the yarn at once, immersion of the yarn into an indigo tank is repeated until the desired tone is obtained. [6] First of all, the fabric is cleansed from the required materials for weaving and ready-made clothing. After that it is washed with "pumice stone" until the desired color is obtained. This stone has an abrasive effect on the fabric and has an anti-adhesive effect for color to stick onto the fabric again. In the following step, the contrast between blue and white is increased by using chemical processes. In the bleaching process, the quantity of chemicals is increased and the color changes to blue ice. In addition, in the "rodeo" stage, bleaching of certain regions is provided by spraying in private cabins.

In the Japanese patent application No. JP19930131162 in 1993, a solution related to denim fabric and its production is described. However, a flexible solution providing comfort for the user in wearing is needed. Description of the objects of the Invention.

The object of the invention considering the state of the art is the development of a new denim fabric in which the existing disadvantages of the structure are removed and the back face is towel-looking and has the comfort of towel[7].

Another object of the invention is to develop a fabric providing comfort for the user of the clothing. Another object of the invention is to provide the healthy use of jeans due to its flexible and formfitting fabric. Another object of the invention is to provide wear comfort, flexibility, double layer fabric feature whose back face is towel-looking, prevention of the contact of indigo dyed yarns with skin or other clothes, easiness and comfort[8]. Another object of the invention is that the developed denim fabric is able to be used on clothing such as pants, shirts, coat etc. Another object of the invention is the formation of loops whose back face is similar to towel due to the layout of the warp and wefts, thereby achieving the desired appearance and expected comfort on fabric[9]. The most common fabric pattern design used in denim is classic 3/1 Z twill. In the present invention front view is close to the classic 3/1 Z twill view and back face is also seen as towel pattern. In order to achieve the above-mentioned objects, a new denim fabric has been developed.

Denim Dyeing Technology

Denim is a rugged cotton twill textile, in which the weft passes under two or more warp fibers. It produces the recognizable diagonal ribbing characteristic on the fabric, which distinguishes denim from cotton duck[10]. It is a twill-weave woven fabric that uses different colours for the warp and weft. One colour mainly used on the fabric surface is indigo blue. This produces an effect of surface dyeing.

There are two types of denim fabric dyeing. They are indigo dyeing and sulphur dyeing. Indigo dyeing produces conventional blue colour and shade alike to blue colour[11]. Sulphur dyeing, which also called colour denim is used to produce particular colours like black, cherry, grey, rust, mustard and lime, and also to get better the quality.

Both of them are vat dyestuff. They are insoluble in water and have a very poor affinity to cellulose fibers like cotton fiber. In normal situation, vat dyes will not attach on cotton fiber[12]. For dyeing of cotton yarn, vat dyes should be transformed into water-soluble form via chemical reduction process, in which hydrogen is liberated. The hydrogen

reacts with the dye and allows a water molecule to attach to the dye. The dye is then transported into cotton fiber by the media of water[13]. Sodium hydrosulfite with sodium hydroxide is one of the reducing agents used to convert the dye to its soluble form. The dye is attached onto cotton fiber by the water. These reduced dyes have to then be oxidized. Oxygen reacts with the hydrogen to produce water. Removing the hydrogen makes the dye insoluble and results in the dye becoming physically trapped inside the fiber. (Ghoranneviss, M.)

In the past, denim has been famous in American custom since the late 18th century. "Denim" came from a French word "serge de Nimes"[14]. Jeans are made from denim fabric and were originally made for labours. In the beginning, jeans were plain working trousers worn by labour. They became trendy among young groups in America in 1950s Because of the popularity of denim products, especially denim jeans, they play as a vital role in fashion and textiles industry[15]. Denim jeans present toughness and a slightly worn look for the fashionable appearance, which is the explanation why denim jeans are welcomed by various public around the world. The fade-out effect can be produced in nature or in manufacture process. Dry denim means unwashed after being dyed. It is recognized to fade gradually as the customer wears the article made of denim[16]. A number of consumers choose this type of denim for the reason that they can "age" their denim in a more natural way and can show their character. Manufacturer developed some unusual washing method on denim merchandises which can make a quick and standardized wash-out effect. It plays a very significant role on denim product development. These methods not only make denim more vintage and create more "high and low" effect in a short time, but also allow mass production for the development of denim market and give more choices for customers[17].

Materials and methods

Fabric Category : Denim (indigo)

Composition : 100% cotton,

Fabric Type : 3/1 'Z' Twill

GSM : 318

Construction : 70 x 42 / 10 x 9

EPI : 70

PPI : 42

Warp Count : 10

Weft Count : 9

Chemicals & Auxiliaries

Genzyme SL, (cellulose enzyme, Sri Lanka) Variable 0.5%, 1%, 2%, 3%, 3.5%

Anti-back staining agent: 0.5 g/l

Detergent (Kohinoor, BD): 0.6g/l

Biological detergent as desizing agent, Germany: 0.6%

Soda ash (Nirma, India):1.2g/l

Acetic acid (China): 1g/l

Textsoft softener (Germany): 1g/l

Equipment

Garments Washing Machine (Front loading).

Chemical Mixture M/C

Hydro Extractor Machine.

Dryer Machine (Steam).

Tensile Strength Machine.

GSM Cutter

Crock meter

Method: Front Loading Washing Machine

Front loading washing machines, otherwise known as horizontal axis washing machines, have gained popularity because many models use less energy and save people money on electric bills[18]. The front loading washing machine uses technology similar to a traditional front loading dryer since the clothes are placed in a stainless steel drum, loaded from the front, and spun[19]. These washers work by filling the bottom of the tub with water and rotating the clothes through the water, instead of wringing the clothes through a central agitator. Because these washers are so different from traditional top load washers, instructions for use also differ greatly. Before using your front load washer, research how best to use and care for it and it will have fewer mechanical problems. This article will show you how to use a front loading washing machine which is shown below in Figure 1.

Fig:1 Front loading Washing Machine

Variable enzyme concentration %: Single factor experiment design analysis based on variable enzyme ratio which is given below in Table 1.

Table: 1

Variable enzyme conc. %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
0.5	40	30
1		
2		
3		
3.5		

In this above experimental single factor analysis we assume the temperature at 40°C and time for 30 minute and just variable concentration % from 0.5% to 3.5%. After finishing the process we found the visual analysis for suitable enzyme concentration % at 1%.

Variable Temp (°C): Single factor experiment design analysis based on variable Temp which is given below in Table 2

Table: 2

Suitable enzyme conc. %	Variable Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	40	30
	45	
	50	
	55	
	60	

From the table 1 we got suitable enzyme concentration% 1%, assume time for 30 minute and variable temperature from 40°C to 60°C.

Changeable Time (Min): Single factor experiment design analysis based on Changeable Time which is given below in Table 3

Table: 3

Suitable enzyme conc. %	Suitable Temp (°C)	Changeable Time (Min)
1	45	30
		35
		40
		45
		55

From the table 2 we got also suitable temperature 45°C and time from 30 minute to 55 minute.

Optimum data analysis: We got the Optimum results from single factor (Visual analysis) above the data analysis which is given below:

Table: 4

Suitable enzyme conc. %	Suitable Temp (°C)	Suitable Time (Min)
1	45	35

Finally, from table 3 we got the suitable time for 35 minutes and suitable temperature 45°C and also enzyme concentration% 1 %.

Result & Discussion

L9 Taguchi Experimental Design analysis

Recent industrial applications have been particularly associated with the name of the Japanese engineer, G. Taguchi. The Taguchi method optimizes design parameters to minimize variation before optimizing design to hit mean target

values for output parameters. The Taguchi method uses special orthogonal arrays to study all the design factors with minimum of experiments. The Taguchi method is one of the best experimental methodologies used to find the minimum number of experiments to be performed within the permissible limit of factors and levels. The comparative study was performed for volumetric wear of Nano hydroxyapatite and MTA-filled dental composites using a combination of four factors, each having five levels. The *S/N* ratio for the smaller is better characteristic was to find the best condition for the minimum volumetric wear rate.

L9 Taguchi Experimental Design analysis: L9 Design

Run	X1	X2	X3
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	2	2	1
5	2	3	2
6	2	1	3
7	3	3	1
8	3	1	2
9	3	2	3

Conc. Of Enzyme (%)	Time (Min)	Temp. (°C)
0.5	30	40
0.5	35	45
0.5	40	50
1	35	40
1	40	45
1	30	50
2	40	40
2	30	45
2	35	50

Taguchi Analysis: Tensile strength warp versus Enzyme conc.%, Temp, Time

Conc. Of Enzyme (%)	Time (Min)	Temp. (°C)	Tensile Strength Warp (lbs)	SNRA 1	MEAN 1
0.5	30	40	274	48.755	274
0.5	35	45	270	48.6273	270
0.5	40	50	256	48.1648	256
1	35	40	247	47.8539	247
1	40	45	241	47.6403	241
1	30	50	238	47.5315	238

2	40	40	233	47.3471	233
2	30	45	229	47.1967	229
2	35	50	224	47.005	224

Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratios: Larger is better

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp	Time
1	48.52	47.99	47.83
2	47.68	47.82	47.83
3	47.18	47.57	47.72
Delta	1.33	0.42	0.11
Rank	1	2	3

Response Table for Means

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp	Time
1	266.7	251.3	247.0
2	242.0	246.7	247.0
3	228.7	239.3	243.3
Delta	38.0	12.0	3.7
Rank	1	2	3

Taguchi Analysis: Tensile strength weft versus Enzyme conc. %, Temp, Time

Conc. Of Enzyme (%)	Time (Min)	Temp. (°C)	Tensile Strength Weft (lbs.)	SNRA 2	MEAN 2
0.5	30	40	175	44.8608	175
0.5	35	45	154	43.7504	154
0.5	40	50	150	43.5218	150
1	35	40	147	43.3463	147
1	40	45	145	43.2274	145
1	30	50	141	42.9844	141
2	40	40	137	42.7344	137
2	30	45	134	42.5421	134
2	35	50	131	42.3454	131

Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratios: Larger is better

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	44.04	43.65	43.46
2	43.19	43.17	43.15
3	42.54	42.95	43.16
Delta	1.50	0.70	0.32
Rank	1	2	3

Response Table for Means

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	159.7	153.0	150.0
2	144.3	144.3	144.0
3	134.0	140.7	144.0
Delta	25.7	12.3	6.0
Rank	1	2	3

Taguchi Analysis: GSM versus Enzyme conc. %, Temp, Time

Conc. Of Enzyme (%)	Time (Min)	Temp. (°C)	GSM	SNRA 3	MEAN 3
0.5	30	40	326	-50.2644	326
0.5	35	45	328	-50.3175	328
0.5	40	50	332	-50.4228	332
1	35	40	334	-50.4749	334
1	40	45	336	-50.5268	336
1	30	50	338	-50.5783	338
2	40	40	341	-50.6551	341
2	30	45	343	-50.7059	343
2	35	50	348	-50.8316	348

Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratio: Smaller is better

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	-50.33	-50.46	-50.52
2	-50.53	-50.52	-50.54
3	-50.73	-50.61	-50.53
Delta	0.40	0.15	0.03
Rank	1	2	3

Response Table for Means

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	328.7	333.7	335.7
2	336.0	335.7	336.7
3	344.0	339.3	336.3
Delta	15.3	5.7	1.0
Rank	1	2	3

Taguchi Analysis: Color rating versus Enzyme conc. %, Temp, Time

Conc. Of Enzyme (%)	Time (Min)	Temp. (°C)	Color Shade (Rating)	SNRA4	MEAN4
0.5	30	40	5	13.9794	5
0.5	35	45	4	12.0412	4
0.5	40	50	4	12.0412	4
1	35	40	4	12.0412	4
1	40	45	3	9.5424	3
1	30	50	4	12.0412	4
2	40	40	3	9.5424	3
2	30	45	3	9.5424	3
2	35	50	3	9.5424	3

Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratio: Larger is better

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	12.687	11.854	11.854
2	11.208	10.375	11.208
3	9.542	11.208	10.375
Delta	3.145	1.479	1.479
Rank	1	2.5	2.5

Response Table for Means

Level	Enzyme conc. %	Temp (°C)	Time (Min)
1	4.333	4.000	4.000
2	3.667	3.333	3.667
3	3.000	3.667	3.333
Delta	1.333	0.667	0.667
Rank	1	2.5	2.5

Concentration of Cellulose Enzyme

Indigo dyed 100% cotton denim garments (trousers) were chemically processed through desizing using Bio.D., soda ash and detergent. Then desized denim garments were processing using cellulose enzyme. The physical and mechanical properties of enzyme treated denim trousers with different concentrations were examined. Results obtained are summarized in above Table (Taguchi Analysis: Tensile strength warp, weft, GSM, color rating). It can be seen from above Table (Taguchi Analysis: Tensile strength warp, weft, GSM, color rating) that, 0.5% concentration cause significant decrease of tensile strength and this decrease was higher at higher enzyme concentrations. It is observed that 2% concentration exhibited the highest decrease in the loss of tensile strength. It is assumed that cellulose enzyme degraded cotton under the conditions used. Cellulose enzyme first attacked on projecting fibers (micro-fibrils) having fabric surface, then attacked on yarn portion, hydrolyzed them slowly. After that it attacked on secondary wall. As a result, cotton fiber loosened and broken down quicker with the frictional forces of rotating cylinder of the washing machine. Denim hydrolysis by measuring the color fading from denim garments was monitored. The results disclose that 1% concentration is the optimum result for color fading. After treatment with cellulose enzyme, the sizes (starch) of warp yarns were removed. As a result bending length was less and softness was increased.

From above Table (Taguchi Analysis: Tensile strength warp, weft, GSM, color rating) also shows that, 0.5% enzyme concentration causes significant increased the GSM (fabric weight) of the garments. During weaving cotton fabrics were subjected to considerable tensions. In subsequent finishing processes such as calendaring this stretch was increased and temporarily set in the fabric. The fabric is then in a state of dimensional instability. This effect is usually greater in the warp direction. This is known as relaxation shrinkage. Due to relaxation shrinkage fabric GSM is increased. Thus, 2% cellulose wash exhibited the higher GSM as compared with the other concentrations. It is selected that 0.5% - 1% enzyme concentration is optimum for denim washing with cellulose enzyme

Temperature of Cellulose Enzyme Treatment

The effect of cellulose in denim garment washing under the influence of 40, 45, 50°C for 30-40 min was investigated. The effect of temperature on loss in tensile strength, color fading, fabric weight, is shown in Table (Taguchi Analysis: Tensile strength warp, weft, GSM, color rating). Temperatures of washing treatment specifically between 55 and 65°C decrease the color shade remarkable what we had done in Single Factor Experiment Design; higher temperature, i.e. 70°C does not cause further decrease in color shade, because the action of enzyme decreased at higher temperature. The effect of temperature on surface roughness is clear particularly when enzyme wash was performed at 55°C – 60°C. It is selected that 40-45°C washing temperature is optimum for denim washing with cellulose enzyme.

Time of Cellulose Enzyme Treatment

The effect of time on denim fabric properties is shown in Table (Taguchi Analysis: Tensile strength warp, weft, GSM, color rating). It effects on fabric strength, color fading, softness, shrinkage and GSM. So considering strength, softness, shrinkage, it is selected that 30-35 min washing time is optimum for denim washing with cellulose enzyme.

Conclusions

The tensile strength, stiffness and color shade decrease after cellulose enzyme washing treatment; meanwhile fabric GSM obtained little bit higher than those of prewashing due to more shrinkage in warp direction. It is further noted that pre-washed denim samples are almost stiff and harder than the enzyme treated cotton denim garments.

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